

Electronic Health Records Systems Using Blockchain

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Abstract—The use of blockchain technology in electronic health record (EHR) systems is examined in this research study. This study seeks to advance the profession by outlining a more secure and open approach for storing and exchanging electronic health records (EHRs) in light of the expanding concerns over data privacy and security in the healthcare sector. This study uses blockchain-based solutions to gain insights into the benefits and drawbacks of implementing blockchain in EHR systems, as well as how it can enhance data privacy, interoperability, and accuracy. The findings of this study can help medical professionals make better choices about patient care, data management, and legal compliance, which will ultimately result in better healthcare outcomes and patient satisfaction.

Keywords—Blockchain, cloud service provider, Electronic health records, Healthcare, Data storage, Data sharing, Security.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electronic health record (EHR) systems have become increasingly popular in recent years as the healthcare sector has undergone a digital transition. By digitising patient records and making them readily available to authorised healthcare practitioners, electronic health record (EHR) systems are intended to enhance patient care. However, there are still some difficulties with interoperability, data accuracy, and data security that traditional EHR systems must contend with. Blockchain technology may be able to help in this situation. EHR systems may be able to provide a more secure, open, and interoperable method of handling patient data by utilising the immutable and decentralised characteristics of blockchain. This study investigates the potential of blockchain technology in EHR systems, concentrating on how it might resolve current issues and enhance patient outcomes. In this article, we'll talk about the advantages and drawbacks of adopting blockchain for electronic health records (EHR), as well as the design and implementation issues that come up while creating such systems. This essay aims to shed light on the potential of blockchain technology to transform the medical field and enhance patient care. At its core, blockchain is a distributed ledger technology that allows for the secure and transparent storage of data across a network of nodes. Each block in the chain contains a timestamped record of transactions, which is encrypted and stored on multiple nodes in the network. This creates a tamper-proof record that can be accessed by authorized parties, while ensuring the privacy and security of patient data. By leveraging blockchain technology, EHR systems can overcome some of the challenges associated with traditional systems. For example, blockchain can facilitate the sharing of health information across disparate systems, while maintaining data integrity and security.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

EHR (electronic health record) systems have grown in popularity recently and offer a number of advantages, including better patient care and enhanced productivity. However, issues with data security, privacy, and interoperability still exist. By providing a decentralised, secure, and transparent mechanism to store and distribute EHR data, blockchain technology has been suggested as a potential answer to these problems.

The application of blockchain technology in EHR systems was investigated in a study by J. Zhang et al. [1]. The authors suggested an electronic health record (EHR) system based on blockchain that would give individuals total control over their health data and guarantee the privacy and security of their personal information. According to the study, the suggested solution might enhance EHR data sharing and lessen data breaches.

Another study by K. L. Kuo et al. investigated the application of blockchain technology in clinical trial EHR systems [2]. The authors suggested a blockchain-based approach that would enable clinical trial participants and researchers to securely and openly share electronic health record (EHR) data. The study discovered that by cutting the time and expenses involved in data exchange, the suggested system could increase the effectiveness and precision of clinical studies.

S. P. Rathore et al. conducted a thorough analysis of blockchain technology's application in healthcare, including EHR systems [3]. According to the analysis, blockchain technology has the potential to solve several of the problems that EHR systems currently face, including data security, privacy, and interoperability. The analysis did, however, also emphasise the need for more study and development to fully realise blockchain technology's promise in the healthcare industry.

Overall, these research show that integrating blockchain technology into EHR systems may have advantages. While more investigation is required to fully understand this technology's potential, it is obvious that blockchain has the power to completely alter how EHR data is shared, stored, and protected.

III. MOTIVATION

Electronic Health Records (EHRs) are critical for ensuring that healthcare providers have accurate and up-to-date information about their patients' medical histories, diagnoses, and treatments. However, patients, healthcare organisations, and providers frequently worry about the security and privacy of EHRs. Blockchain technology can help in this situation. Providers and patients can feel more secure about the confidentiality and privacy of their medical information by adopting blockchain to store EHRs. Blockchain offers a decentralised, tamper-proof ledger that prevents unauthorised parties from changing or manipulating EHRs.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to develop an electronic health record system using blockchain technology. The methodology for electronic health record (HER) system using blockchain includes the following steps:

- A. **Data Collection:** The data for this project will be collected from various healthcare organizations, including hospitals, clinics, and private practices. The dataset will contain patient health records, including medical history, diagnoses, treatment plans, and medications. The data will be anonymized to protect patient privacy and will be stored on a distributed ledger using blockchain technology.
- B. **Data Pre-processing:** The collected data will be pre-processed to ensure data quality and integrity. This will involve data cleaning, data transformation, and data normalization to prepare the data for use in the blockchain network. Additionally, a consensus mechanism will be implemented to ensure the validity of the data and prevent malicious activities, such as tampering and hacking.
- C. **Model Building:** The EHR system will be built on top of the blockchain network using smart contract technology. The smart contracts will enable secure and transparent access to patient health records, ensuring that only authorized parties can view and update the data. The system will also include features such as patient consent management, data sharing, and data analytics.
- D. **Analyzing:** The performance of the EHR system will be analyzed using metrics such as data accuracy, system availability, and user satisfaction. Data analytics will be performed on the stored data to generate insights into patient health outcomes and healthcare trends. Additionally, security audits will be conducted to ensure the system's resilience against cyber threats.
- E. **Result:** The final EHR system will provide a secure and efficient platform for healthcare organizations to store, manage, and share patient health records. The use of blockchain technology will ensure the integrity and privacy of the data, while smart contract technology will enable automated and secure data transactions. The system will also provide valuable insights into patient health outcomes and healthcare trends, supporting

evidence-based decision-making and improving the quality of care.

V. BUILD MODEL

Building a model of an Electronic Health Record (EHR) system using blockchain technology involves several key steps:

1. **Identify the Use Case:** Start by identifying the specific use case for the EHR system. Who will use it? What information needs to be stored? What type of transactions will be performed? Answering these questions will help you determine the specific features and functionality that the system needs to have.
2. **Choose the Blockchain Platform:** Choose a blockchain platform that best suits your needs. There are several blockchain platforms available, such as Ethereum, Hyperledger Fabric, and Corda, each with its unique strengths and weaknesses. Consider factors such as scalability, security, and ease of use when selecting a platform.
3. **Define the Smart Contract:** Define the smart contract that will govern the transactions on the blockchain. Smart contracts are self-executing programs that can automate the execution of agreements between parties. In the context of EHRs, smart contracts can be used to enforce privacy and security rules, automate the sharing of patient data, and manage access controls.
4. **Establish the Network:** Establish the network infrastructure for the EHR system. This includes setting up the nodes and connecting them to the blockchain network. Nodes are responsible for verifying and validating transactions, maintaining the integrity of the blockchain, and ensuring that the data on the blockchain is consistent.
5. **Develop the Front-end Application:** Develop a user-friendly front-end application that allows users to interact with the EHR system. The front-end application should be designed to make it easy for patients, doctors, and other stakeholders to access and share patient data securely and seamlessly.
6. **Integrate with Existing Systems:** Integrate the EHR system with existing healthcare systems, such as hospital information systems, electronic medical records, and clinical decision support systems. This will enable the EHR system to work seamlessly with other healthcare IT systems, improving the overall efficiency of the healthcare system.
7. **Implement Data Privacy and Security Measures:** Implement data privacy and security measures to protect patient data. Blockchain technology offers inherent security features such as immutability, decentralization, and consensus mechanisms, but additional measures may be required to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of patient data.
8. **Test and Deploy:** Test the EHR system thoroughly to ensure that it meets the required performance, security, and usability standards. Once testing is complete, deploy the system and train users on how to use it effectively.

9. Adding HER request to the HER server:

```
def addEhrRequest(request):
    if request.method == 'POST':
        inputData = EHR()
        inputData.patient_fname = request.POST.get('fname')
        inputData.patient_lname = request.POST.get('lname')
        inputData.email = request.POST.get('email')
        data = {'name': request.POST.get('fname') + request.POST.get('lname'), 'email': request.POST.get('email'), 'hospitalId': 'G6'}
        response = requests.post('http://localhost:8000/ehr/add', data=data)
        if response.status_code == 201:
            data = response.json()
            inputData.ehr_id = data['ehrId']

        inputData.ehr_status = "registerd"
        inputData.save()
        data = {'code': 200}
        json_data = json.dumps(data)
        return HttpResponse(json_data, status=status.HTTP_201_CREATED, content_type='application/json')
```

```
# Upload merged file to Firebase storage
merged_file_name = str(uuid.uuid4()) + '.pdf'
blob = bucket.blob(merged_file_name)
blob.upload_from_string(merged_file.getvalue(), content_type='application/pdf')

# Get download URL of uploaded file
url = blob.generate_signed_url(datetime.timedelta(seconds=300), method='GET')

# update in ehr server
data = {'ehrId': ehrId, 'documentLink': url}
response = requests.post('http://localhost:8000/records/add', data=data)
if response.status_code == 201:
    data = {'code': 200}
    return HttpResponse(json.dumps(data), status=status.HTTP_201_CREATED, content_type='application/json')
else:
    return HttpResponse('Error')

else:
    return HttpResponse('Error')
```

10. Verify and accept EHR request from the EHR server:

```
def acceptEhrRequest(request, id):
    if request.method == 'GET':
        m = EHR.objects.get(id=id)
        data = {'name': m.patient_fname + m.patient_lname, 'email': m.email, 'hospitalId': 'G6'}
        response = requests.post('http://localhost:8000/ehr/add', data=data)
        if response.status_code == 201:
            data = response.json()
            m.ehr_id = data['ehrId']

        m.ehr_status = "registerd"
        m.save()
        data = {'code': 200}
        return HttpResponse(json.dumps(data), status=status.HTTP_201_CREATED, content_type='application/json')
```

11. Upload test reports by the doctor:

```
def uploadTest(request):
    if request.method == 'POST':
        # Get form data and uploaded image
        name = request.POST.get('name')
        prescription = request.POST.get('prescription')
        description = request.POST.get('description')
        ehrId = request.POST.get('ehrId')
        image = request.FILES.get('image_file')

        # Create a PDF file
        buffer = io.BytesIO()
        p = canvas.Canvas(buffer)
        p.drawString(100, 750, "title: {}".format(name))
        p.drawString(100, 700, "prescription: {}".format(prescription))
        p.drawString(100, 650, "description: {}".format(description))
        p.showPage()
        p.save()
        buffer.seek(0)

        # Merge PDF file with uploaded image
        pdf_merger = PdfMerger()
        pdf_merger.append(PdfReader(buffer))
        pdf_merger.append(PdfReader(image))
        merged_file = io.BytesIO()
        pdf_merger.write(merged_file)
        merged_file.seek(0)
```

VI. CONCLUSION

To conclude, the use of blockchain technology in electronic health records (EHRs) has the potential to revolutionize the way medical information is stored and shared. Blockchain technology can guarantee the security and privacy of private patient information while also enhancing accessibility and interoperability amongst various healthcare providers. Blockchain can improve openness and confidence in the healthcare system by offering a tamper-proof and auditable trace of every transaction, thereby improving patient outcomes. However, there are still many obstacles in the way of blockchain EHR adoption, such as standardised protocols requirements, technical complexity, and regulatory concerns. The advantages of this technology, however, indicate that it will remain a focus of intensive study and development in the healthcare industry. Blockchain-based EHRs can improve patient engagement by giving patients more control over their health data, allowing them to share it with providers and researchers as they see fit. The use of smart contracts can also enable automatic payment processing and insurance claim management, streamlining administrative processes and reducing healthcare costs.

VI. REFERENCES

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